

Investigation on heavy metal content in common grown vegetables from polluted sites of Moradabad district, India

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Abstract : Vegetables growing on heavy metal contaminated soils can accumulate high concentrations of trace elements and may pose serious health risk to consumers. Essential trace elements (Fe, Zn, Mn, Cr) were analyzed in edible and non-edible parts of six vegetables i.e. palak, bathua, shalgam, cauliflower, cabbage and coriander collected from Dhaurinala and Karula nala at Moradabad district using AAS. Concentration of Cr in all vegetables and Zn in Dhauri palak roots and leaves, Karula nala bathua roots and leaves and Karula nala shalgam crossed the tolerable limits for human consumption. Transfer factor of Cr was observed to be maximum. There was risk of consumption of examined vegetables, as daily intake for chromium was above the tolerable daily intake value.

Keywords : Heavy metals, daily intake, transfer factor, vegetables, polluted site.

Introduction

Heavy metals are very toxic both in elemental and soluble salt forms. Their presence in the atmosphere, soil and water, even in traces can cause serious problems to organisms¹. Heavy metals are harmful because of their xenobiotic nature, long biological half lives and their capacity to accumulate in different parts of plants animals. Even at low concentrations, they show damaging effects to humans and animals because there is no mechanism for their elimination from the body^{2,3}. Food and water are not only the main sources of essential metals, but are also the media through which we are exposed to various toxic metals. Heavy metals are easily accumulated in the edible parts of leafy vegetables⁴.

Some aromatic and medicinal plants are also capable of accumulating heavy metals from contaminated soil⁵. All heavy metals, both essential (iron; Fe, zinc; Zn; manganese; Mn, chromium; Cr, copper; Cu, nickel; Ni) and non essential (cadmium; Cd, lead; Pb) can cause toxic effects to plants and humans if found in high concentration⁶. Uptake of metals is dependent on chemical forms of metals in the contaminated soil⁷. Several studies have indicated that vegetables, grown in heavy metal contaminated soils accumulated high amount of the metals⁸⁻¹⁰. Vegetables absorb and adsorb these metals from the ground as well as from the parts of vegetable exposed to air from

polluted environment¹¹.

A lot of research on heavy metal content in different types of organic wastes such as industrial sludge¹², compost^{13,14} and transfer to the soil and crops¹⁵⁻¹⁹ has been undertaken. Moradabad, a city of brass industry in Uttara Pradesh, India, has a high degree of air, water and soil pollution²⁰. Dumping site for most of the industrial sewage sludge is Ram Ganga River through various drains. This waste has been used as fertilizer in agricultural soils. So, this could be a good source of heavy metals. The aim of the present study was to examine heavy metals (chromium, manganese, zinc and iron) content of some of the commonly grown vegetables in sewage sludge amended soils of Moradabad. The daily intake of the examined metals for adults and children is also calculated.

Results and discussion

The collected soil samples were analyzed for their physicochemical properties. The percentage organic carbon ranged from 3.162–0.867%. The pH ranged from neutral (Dhauri nala soil - 7.150) to slightly alkaline (Karula nala soil - 7.890). Electrical conductivity ranged from 0.431 dS m⁻¹ (Dhauri soil) to 0.630 dS m⁻¹ (Karula nala soil). The texture of the soil collected from Dhauri was loamy sand while from Karula nala soil was sandy clay loam (Table 1).

The results of the metal analysis in tested soils indicated that concentrations of heavy metals (mg kg^{-1}) ranged from a minimum of 141.00 to a maximum of 544.00 for Zn, 361.00 to 478.00 for Mn, 50.00 to 131.00 for Cr and 1570.1 to 1594.43 for Fe (Table 2). Although micronutrients such as zinc (Zn) and copper (Cu) are essential for plant growth and human nutrition at low doses, they may be toxic for humans, animals and plants at high doses²¹.

Zinc (Zn) :

Zinc is considered to be an important factor in the biosynthesis of some enzymes and proteins^{22,23}. The permissible concentration of Zn²⁴ in plant is 50 mg kg^{-1} . In the investigated plant materials, the highest zinc content was found in Dhauri palak leaves (258 mg kg^{-1}) while the lowest was detected in *Coriandrum sativum* leaves (7 mg kg^{-1}). The concentration of Zn was beyond permissible limit in Dhauri palak roots, Dhauri palak leaves, Karula Bathua roots, Bathua leaves and Karula shalgam.

Chromium (Cr) :

Chromium is a naturally occurring element found in rocks, plants, soil, volcanic dust and gases. Human being can be exposed to chromium by taking chromium contaminated food, water and air. Excessive amount can cause some diseases such as lungs and gastrointestinal cancers²⁵.

In the tested plant samples, the lowest content of chromium i.e. 63.5 mg kg^{-1} was observed in Dhauri palak roots and the maximum concentration was estimated as 361.5 mg kg^{-1} in Karula cabbage leaves. The tolerable limit for crops set by Awasthi²⁴ was 20.00 mg kg^{-1} . It was found that all the tested plants accumulate Cr above this limit.

Manganese (Mn) :

The mean content of manganese (Mn) varied with the values between 10.0 mg kg^{-1} in *Coriandrum* leaves and 293 mg kg^{-1} in Dhauri palak leaves. The permissible limit set by Kabata and Pendias²⁵ in edible plants is $20\text{--}500 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$. All the plants accumulate Mn below this limit.

Iron (Fe) :

Iron is necessary for the biosynthesis of haemoglobin and plays an important role in oxygen and electron transfer in human body²⁶.

In the studied plants, Fe content was in the following order : *Coriandrum* leaves < Cauliflower < Cabbage < *Coriandrum* roots < Spinach leaves < Turnip roots <

Table 1. Physicochemical property of soil samples

Sites	pH	EC (dS m^{-1})	OC (%)	Texture	Total Zn (mg kg^{-1})	Total Mn (mg kg^{-1})	Total Cr (mg kg^{-1})	Total Fe (mg kg^{-1})
Dhauri nala soil	7.150 ± 0.062	0.60 ± 0.30	3.162 ± 0.187	Loamy sand	141.00 ± 1.83	478.00 ± 27.24	50.00 ± 0.82	1594.43 ± 157.97
Karula nala soil	7.890 ± 0.256	0.43 ± 0.15	0.867 ± 0.153	Sandy clay loam	544.00 ± 7.07	361.00 ± 2.16	131.00 ± 2.45	1570.1 ± 29.12

EC = Electrical conductivity; OC = Organic carbon.

Table 2. Metal content in vegetables collected from two contaminated sites

Vegetables	Mn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	Cr (mg kg ⁻¹)	Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)
Dhauri Palak (Root)	149.0 ± 8.25	619.5 ± 18.16	63.5 ± 3.56	240 ± 3.92
Dhauri Palak (Leaves)	293.0 ± 10.10	1133.5 ± 25.94	301.5 ± 5.03	258 ± 16.52
KN Bathua (Root)	203.0 ± 14.85	1311 ± 19.68	81.5 ± 1.15	130 ± 5.60
KN Bathua (Leaves)	91.0 ± 9.90	852.5 ± 5.69	269.5 ± 21.59	220.5 ± 2.16
KN Palak (Root)	129.0 ± 11.58	645.5 ± 5.07	301.5 ± 9.02	48.5 ± 4.08
KN Palak (Leaves)	75.0 ± 2.58	392.5 ± 21.68	322.5 ± 3.69	39 ± 2.16
KN Shalgam (Roots)	40.0 ± 12.03	555.5 ± 8.13	156 ± 9.42	60.5 ± 3.56
KN Cauliflower	67.5 ± 9.15	323.2 ± 7.75	277.5 ± 16.22	13.5 ± 2.16
KN Cabbage	50.5 ± 4.65	332.5 ± 15.77	361.5 ± 23.78	76 ± 0.82
KN Coriander (Roots)	25.5 ± 3.11	367 ± 15.19	316.5 ± 4.54	15 ± 2.71
KN Coriander (Leaves)	10.0 ± 2.16	250 ± 8.37	125 ± 2.16	7 ± 1.41

Dhauri palak leaves < Bathua leaves < Bathua roots. The highest concentration of Fe have been detected in Bathua roots and lowest was detected in *Coriandrum* leaves. In all the vegetables, heavy metals were higher than the recommended tolerable levels proposed by joint WHO/FAO²⁷ expert committee on food additives.

Transfer factor :

Among examined metals, Cr showed maximum values for transfer factor, ranged from 0.95 (KN Coriander) to 6.03 (Dhauri palak leaves) and it was minimum for Mn, ranging from 0.03 (KN Coriander root) to 0.61 (Dharui palak). Transfer factor for Mn, Cr and Zn was highest for Dharui palak and for Fe, was highest in KN Bathua (Fig. 1). Differences in the concentration of metals in soil and different kind of vegetables may cause

variations in transfer factor^{28,29}. Singh *et al.*³⁰ observed that among all the vegetables, transfer factor of Cd was highest except for radish and tomato at waste water irrigated site, which showed that Cd is more mobile than other metals. Lokeshwari and Chandrappa³¹ have reported that Cd is more mobile than other metals because it retained less strongly by the soil.

Daily intake of metals (DIM) :

The degree of toxicity of heavy metals depends upon pathways of exposure to the targeted organisms and thus food chain and finally their daily intake. Heavy metal intake through consumption of vegetables grown in Moradabad showed large variation listed in Table 3.

The highest intakes of Fe, Zn, Mn and Cr were from the consumption of Karula nala (KN), Bathua roots, Dhauri

Fig. 1. Transfer factors of Mn, Fe, Cr and Zn in different vegetables.

Table 3. Daily intake of tested metals

Vegetables	Mn			Fe			Cr			Zn					
	Daily intake of metal (DIM) adult (mg)	Daily intake of metal (DIM) child (mg)	Dietary intake limit 1.6-2.3 (mg/day ³²)	Daily intake of metal (DIM) adult (mg)	Daily intake of metal (DIM) child (mg)	Dietary intake limit 7-10 (mg/day ³²)	Daily intake of metal (DIM) adult (mg)	Daily intake of metal (DIM) child (mg)	Dietary intake limit 20-35 (µg/day ³²)	Daily intake of metal (DIM) adult (mg)	Daily intake of metal (DIM) child (mg)	Dietary intake limit 11-15 (µg/day ³²)	Daily intake of metal (DIM) adult (mg)	Daily intake of metal (DIM) child (mg)	Dietary intake limit 3-5 (mg/day ³²)
	Dhauri Palak (Root)	0.078	0.005	0.005	0.325	0.374	0.374	0.033	0.038	0.033	0.126	0.145	0.038	0.126	0.145
Dhauri Palak (Leaves)	0.154	0.006	0.006	0.595	0.684	0.684	0.158	0.182	0.158	0.135	0.156	0.182	0.135	0.156	0.156
KN Bathua (Root)	0.106	0.009	0.009	0.688	0.791	0.791	0.043	0.049	0.043	0.068	0.078	0.049	0.068	0.078	0.078
KN Bathua (Leaves)	0.048	0.006	0.006	0.447	0.514	0.514	0.141	0.163	0.141	0.116	0.133	0.163	0.116	0.133	0.133
KN Palak (Root)	0.068	0.007	0.007	0.339	0.389	0.389	0.158	0.182	0.158	0.025	0.029	0.182	0.025	0.029	0.029
KN Palak (Leaves)	0.039	0.002	0.002	0.206	0.237	0.237	0.169	0.194	0.169	0.02	0.024	0.194	0.02	0.024	0.024
KN Shalgam (Roots)	0.021	0.007	0.007	0.291	0.335	0.335	0.082	0.094	0.082	0.032	0.036	0.094	0.032	0.036	0.036
KN Cauliflower	0.035	0.006	0.006	0.17	0.195	0.195	0.146	0.167	0.146	0.007	0.008	0.167	0.007	0.008	0.008
KN Cabbage	0.026	0.003	0.003	0.174	0.201	0.201	0.190	0.218	0.190	0.04	0.046	0.218	0.04	0.046	0.046
KN Coriander (Roots)	0.013	0.002	0.002	0.193	0.221	0.221	0.166	0.191	0.166	0.008	0.009	0.191	0.008	0.009	0.009
KN Coriander (Leaves)	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.131	0.151	0.151	0.066	0.075	0.066	0.004	0.004	0.075	0.004	0.004	0.004

palak leaves, Dhauri palak leaves and KN cabbage respectively. Our calculated daily intake for all the metals except chromium were below the tolerable daily intake recommended by Institute of Medicine³². Thus, daily intake rates for Cr were above dietary limits and there may be risk of chromium accumulation due to studied vegetable consumption. Previous reports on daily intake of metals also suggested that there is no risk due to consumption of common foodstuff grown under waste water irrigated areas^{33,34}. On the other hand, Singh *et al.*³⁰ found that daily intake rates for Cd in palak and *Amaranthus* were above the tolerable daily intake.

Data on percent contribution of heavy metals in daily intake by different kinds of vegetables is shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. Leafy vegetables were observed to have the highest percentage contribution to the daily intake of all metals. However, second highest concentration of Mn and Cr was shown by inflorescence vegetables while concentration of Fe and Zn in root vegetables. Availability of leafy vegetable during collection period may be the cause of higher contribution of daily intake of all metals (Fig. 2). Among metals, percent contribution of leafy vegetables towards daily intake was in the order : Zn > Mn > Fe > Cr. In case of inflorescence vegetables the percent contribution towards daily intake was : Cr > Fe > Mn > Zn while of root vegetables it was : Fe > Zn > Cr > Mn (Fig. 3).

Materials and method :

Plant material :

Edible (leaves and roots) and non edible (roots) parts of seven vegetables viz. Bathua (*Chenopodium album* L.), Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.), Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* L.), Cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis*), Turnip (*Brassica rapa* L.) were collected from Karula nala (KN) while Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.) roots and leaves and Coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) leaves and roots have been collected from Dhauri nala (DN) of Moradabad district during June 2012.

Sample preparation :

All the collected samples of various vegetables were firstly washed with tap water to remove airborne pollutants and then vegetables were washed with 0.1 N HCl and finally with double distilled water. The vegetable samples were weighed and air dried for a day to reduce

Fig. 2. Percent contribution of different kinds of vegetables to daily intake of metals.

Fig. 3. Difference among percent contribution of vegetables to daily intake of heavy metals.

water content. All the samples were then oven-dried in hot air oven at 70–80 °C for 24 h, to remove all moisture. Dried samples were powdered using a pestle and mortar and sieved.

Digestion of soil and vegetable samples :

For heavy metal extraction, two gram of soil was taken with 8 mL of Aqua-regia (HCl and HNO₃ in 3 : 1) in a conical flask and then 10 mL 2% HNO₃ was added and

final solution was filtered into 50 mL volumetric flask and make upto the mark with distilled water³¹. Dried sample of plant (0.1 g) was digested in 100 ml of HNO₃, 10 ml H₂SO₄ and 40 ml HClO₄ mixture (10 : 4 : 1) at 80 °C until a transparent solution was obtained³⁵. These transparent solutions were then filtered through Whatman No. 42 and diluted to 50 ml with distilled water.

Heavy metal analysis :

The concentration of heavy metals in the filtrate was determined by using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (GBC, Australia) fitted with specific lamp of particular metal using appropriate drift blanks.

Physicochemical properties of soil :

The pH of soil and sludge samples was measured in 1 : 2, soil/sludge-water suspension³⁵ using digital pH meter (Systronics 335). Electrical conductivity of soil and sludge samples was determined in 1 : 2 soil/sludge-water extract³⁶ using EC meter (Systronics 304). Soil texture was determined by method given by Kilmer and Alexander³⁷. Percent organic carbon content in the soil/sludge was determined according to the modified Wakley and Black method³⁸.

Data analysis :

Transfer factor :

To understand the risk and associated hazards due to sewage irrigation and sludge addition as fertilizer on agricultural fields and consequent heavy metal accumulation in the grown vegetables, it was necessary to calculate Transfer factor (TF)²⁸.

TF = Concentration of metal in vegetables/Concentration of metal in soil.

Daily intake of metals (DIM) :

The daily intake of metals (DIM) was calculated by the following equation.

$$\text{DIM} = [\text{M}][\text{K}][\text{I}]/\text{W}$$

M = Heavy metal concentration in plants (mg kg⁻¹), K = conversion factor (0.085)³⁹, I = daily intake of vegetables.

(For adults = 0.345 kg/person/day)

(For children = 0.232 kg/person/day)^{40,41}

W = Average body weight

(For adults = 55.9 kg)

(For children = 32.7 kg)

Conclusion

Our results suggested that Cr concentration for all the vegetables and Zn concentrations for Dhauri palak roots, Dhauri palak leaves, Karula Bathua roots, Karula Bathua leaves and Karula shalgam were above the tolerable limits fixed by Indian Standards. Transfer factor for chromium was maximum among all the tested metals. Daily intake results revealed that consumption of these vegetables was risk free with as far as health concern. Sewage irrigation and sludge application as fertilizer led to the accumulation of heavy metals in soil and consequently into the vegetables. Consumption of vegetables with elevated levels of heavy metals may lead to health disorders and the detrimental impact becomes apparent only after several years. So, regular monitoring of heavy metals contamination in the vegetable grown at sewage irrigated and sludge amended area is necessary and consumption of contaminated vegetables should be avoided to reduce health risk.

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